

The Effect of Bilingualism on Cognitive Flexibility of Iranian Female Teenagers

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigated the effect of bilingualism on cognitive flexibility of Iranian female teenagers. To attain the purpose of the study, 100 Iranian monolingual and bilingual high school students were selected. They were aged between 14-16 years old. The researcher used cognitive flexibility inventory to gather the required data. The questionnaire was used to assess the participant level of cognitive flexibility. To assess the normality of the obtained data from the questionnaire, One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test was performed. The researcher used descriptive statistics and Independent Samples t Tests to compare the scores of monolinguals and bilinguals. The results revealed that bilingualism had a significant effect on Iranian teenagers' cognitive flexibility. In other words, bilingual students showed higher levels of cognitive flexibility. The findings have implications for experts in the field of second language learning.

Keywords: Effect of Bilingualism, Cognitive Flexibility, Iranian Female Teenagers, language

1. INTRODUCTION

There is a general consensus that individuals are different in their abilities to perform certain tasks. One of these abilities is cognitive ability. Safronova [1] defines cognitive abilities as capabilities involved in thinking such as reasoning, perception, memory. Cognitive abilities includes "memory, inhibitory control, selective attention, decision making, planning, sustain attention, social cognition and cognitive flexibility" [2]. Cognitive flexibility refers to the ability to neatly switch between different thoughts and actions in a given situation [3].

Individuals are not the same in their cognitive characteristics; these differences may result in some uniqueness, and may have some reasons too [1]. Language could be a reason. It is assumed that language has a role in the way of individual thinking or behavior and it could be the cause of many other differences. It is possible that monolinguals and bilinguals differ regarding cognition and its subdivisions including memory, attention and style [1]. Language is one of our most articulated means that is used mainly for expressing ideas and thoughts [4]. There is a science of language that considers language as a means of expressing ideas and thoughts. This science of the study of language is known as the cognitive perspective [4]. "In the cognitive perspective, language is considered as part of a cognitive system which involves perception, emotions, categorization, abstraction processes, and reasoning. These cognitive abilities all interact with language and are influenced by language" [4].

It is clear that language is a means for communication, and some of the people all around the world use more than one language in their daily communication. Some research have found particular benefits related to speaking two languages [5, 6], some have found monolingual benefits in especial fields such as vocabulary [7, 8] while others have found no influence of speaking two languages at all [9, 10]. Speaking two languages may affect different characteristics of individuals including cognitive abilities which are generally given little attention in the language-teaching classrooms in Iran. Since cognitive abilities play a significant role in individuals' life, finding new factors that have some positive effects on it is of great importance [8].

Önen and Koçak [11] studied the influence of cognitive flexibility on high school students' strategies in studying. 554 high school students participated in this study. The researchers used the scale of Cognitive Flexibility to gather the required data for this research. The results of the study revealed that there was a strong correlation between the level of students' Cognitive Flexibility and the kinds of strategies that they used in their studies.

In another study [12], studied how cognitive flexibility affects positive emotions to improve creativity. 120 students took part in this study and they were randomly assigned to positive, neutral or negative affect situations. The researcher used a switch activity to assess the levels of cognitive flexibility. Then the participants' creative performances were investigated by either an open-ended divergent thinking exam or a closed-ended attitude problem-solving activity. The findings revealed that positive emotional states can decrease switch costs and improve both kinds of creative tasks. However, cognitive flexibility indicated a complete mediating influence only on the correlation between positive affect and insight problem solving, but not between positive affect and divergent thought.

The significance of the present study lies on the fact that it looks out the relationship between cognition and language from a different perspective. Therefore, the findings of the present research might contribute to further research by focusing on and in the light of future theories about second language acquisition. The results of this study also might provide further evidence for individual differences in their cognitive ability. Furthermore, since the cognitive ability is important in learning, this study shows if learning more languages leads to having a higher level of cognitive ability.

2. Method

A total of 100 Iranian high school female students participated in this study. The researcher used the intact classes of students in a high school in Kermanshah. Fifty students were bilinguals who were native speakers of Kurdish and they were able to speak Persian too. The other participants of this study were monolinguals who were only able to speak Persian. The age range of the participants was 14-16. The researcher used available sampling in this study. They were screened according to their self-reporting. That is they were first asked to answer if they use only Persian in their routines or speak in other languages too. To control the influential variable, all the participants were selected from the same school and same major. The overall mean of the students were also considered to make sure that they are homogeneous. So, the students of the one SD below and above the mean in GPA were selected.

2. 1. Instruments

The Cognitive Flexibility Inventory [13] was used to investigate participants' cognitive flexibility. It is a 20-item Likert-style scale designed to measure the ability to generate alternatives. Item responses are rated from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 7 (Strongly Agree). Total scores range from 20 to 140 with higher scores indicating greater cognitive flexibility. The questionnaire was proved to be valid according to the authors and cronbach's alpha of this questionnaire was 0.91, and test-retest reliability was good ($r = .81, p < .001$) and acceptable.

2. 2. Data Analysis

To assess the normality of the obtained data from the questionnaires, One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test was performed. The researcher used descriptive statistics and Independent Samples t Tests to compare the scores of monolingual and bilingual learners. All of the stages of data analysis have been done using SPSS 21.00 software.

3. Results

3. 1. Examining the Normality of Data

Before doing the analysis of data, normality of collected data was measured using One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. This test was performed to find the normality of distribution of data and to make decision about using parametric or nonparametric test to analyze data. In this statistics test, when significance is less than 0.05, the distribution of data is not normal and it is not possible to use parametric tests. When significance is more than 0.05, the distribution of data is normal and it is possible to use parametric tests. The results of this test are reported in Table (1).

Table (1)
One-Sample Kolmogorov- Smirnow Test of Cognitive Flexibility of Monolingual and Bilingual Learners

		Cognitive flexibility
N		100
Normal Parameters ^a	Mean	77.74
	Std. Deviation	35.63
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.091
	Positive	.091
	Negative	-.072
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.909
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.381

a. Test distribution is Normal.

The above table shows the results of One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnow Test of cognitive flexibility. Since, for all of the variables the significance was more than 0.05, the results showed that the data of all of the tests are normal, accordingly, it was possible to use parametric tests to analyze data.

3. 2. Addressing the Research Question

The research question of the study was: Does bilingualism have a significant effect on cognitive flexibility of Iranian teenagers?

To answer the first research question and to find the possible effect of bilingualism on cognitive flexibility of Iranian teenagers, a set of descriptive statistics and a t-test was performed. The aim of this test was to compare the level of cognitive flexibility of monolingual and bilingual learners. The next table shows the descriptive statistics of the participants' cognitive flexibility.

Table (2)
Descriptive Statistics of Cognitive Flexibility of Monolingual and Bilingual Learners

	groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
cognitive flexibility	monolinguals	50	92.92	10.01	1.41
	bilinguals	50	107.44	21.64	3.06

Table (2) shows the descriptive statistics of the level of cognitive flexibility of monolingual and bilingual learners. According to this table, the mean score of cognitive flexibility of monolingual and bilingual learners are 92.92 and 107.44, respectively. The Std. Deviation of cognitive flexibility of monolingual and bilingual learners are 10.01 and 21.64, respectively. As it is clear from this table, the mean score of bilingual learners is higher than the monolingual learners. It shows that bilingual learners enjoy higher level of cognitive flexibility than monolingual learners. To find out whether this difference is statistically significant, the researcher used an independent samples t-test. The result of this test is reported in the next table.

Table (3)
Independent Sample t Test of Cognitive Flexibility of Monolingual and Bilingual Learners

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
cognitive flexibility	Equal variances assumed	2.53	.000	-4.30	98	.000	1.45	3.37	2.12	7.82
	Equal variances not assumed			-4.30	6.90	.000	1.45	3.37	2.12	7.79

According to Table (3), there is a significant statistical difference between the monolingual and bilingual groups in terms of their level of cognitive flexibility (Significance is less than 0.05, i.e., 0.00). Accordingly,

there was a significant difference between the levels of cognitive flexibility of two groups. The following figure shows the mean score of cognitive flexibility of monolingual and bilingual learners.

Figure (1) Mean scores of cognitive flexibility of monolingual and bilingual learners

The above figure shows the mean score of cognitive flexibility of monolingual and bilingual learners.

Conclusion

The ability to speak two or more languages may bring benefits to individuals since it leads to higher level of cognitive ability. There is a general consensus that bilingual individuals have an advantage in cognitive and mental skill and cognitive flexibility. "The dominant belief at this time is that there is a superiority of divergent thinking abilities among bilinguals" [14]. Moreover Baker [15] believes that "Bilingualism is to intelligence as food is to human fitness A simple statement about bilingualism and intelligence is as impossible as prescribing one simple food for human survival" (p.23). Bilingual individuals offer an opportunity for scholars' to assess the relations between language and cognitive abilities [16]. Bilingual learners have benefits in education, because of their cognitive abilities and mental flexibility.

This study, which intended to examine the effect of second language learning on Iranian teenagers' cognitive flexibility, had some findings. The results showed that second language learning has a significant effect on Iranian teenagers' cognitive flexibility. This finding implies that bilingual teenagers have a higher level of cognitive flexibility than monolinguals. In summary, bilingual students were different from monolingual students in terms of their level of cognitive flexibility. Based on the obtained results and in line with previous studied, the researcher concluded that bilingual individuals enjoy higher level of cognitive ability in compare to monolingual individuals and it could be attributed to their ability to speak two languages.

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